

Online Condition Monitoring for Resonant Tank Capacitors in LLC Converters Using Voltage Gain

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Abstract—LLC converters are extensively utilized in high-power, high-density applications due to their zero-voltage switching capabilities and galvanic isolation, with the resonant tank being considered a critical component for achieving efficient power conversion. However, the resonant tank capacitor is particularly susceptible to aging and eventual failure, as it is subjected to high-frequency charging and discharging cycles that accelerate wear and degradation. To address this issue, a new capacitance estimation method has been presented, specifically designed for the online condition monitoring of the resonant tank capacitor. An in-depth analysis is provided on the voltage gain characteristics of resonant tank to accurately estimate capacitance values, thereby enabling proactive detection of capacitor degradation. Notably, the need for additional external circuitry is eliminated by this approach, simplifying implementation and reducing costs. Simulation studies have been conducted to verify the performance and effectiveness of the proposed method.

Index Terms—Condition monitoring, LLC converter, Resonant tank capacitor

I. INTRODUCTION

LLC converters are widely employed in power systems due to their capability to regulate output voltages across the entire load range with minimal switching frequency variations and achieve zero-voltage switching (ZVS) for primary-side switches and zero-current switching for secondary-side rectifiers [1]. Despite these advantages, degradation and failures are common in LLC converters. Research indicates that capacitor failures account for 30% of all converter failures, representing the highest failure rate [2], which highlights a pressing need for effective methods to monitor capacitor health.

Capacitor Condition Monitoring (CM) can be conducted using various degradation indicators, such as changes in weight, internal pressure, temperature, sound emissions, and electrical properties [3]. Tab. I summarizes these indicators and their corresponding acquisition methods [4]. Among these, electrical indicators are most commonly studied due to their

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TABLE I: Degradation indicators.

Indicators		Indicator acquisition methods
Electrical	R_{ESR} , C , Z_c , etc.	LCR meter, etc. Parameters estimation
Non-electrical	Structure	X-ray image meter
		Optical inspection meter
		Thermography meter
		Acoustic detection meter
	Temperature	Thermography meter Internal temperature
	Weight	Weighing meter
	Pressure	Internal pressure sensor

ability to provide precise and quantifiable insights into capacitor health. Key metrics, including equivalent series resistance (ESR) (R_{ESR}) and capacitance (C), are frequently used as benchmarks for determining the end-of-life (EOL) [5].

These indicators can be estimated through either offline or online techniques [6]. Offline monitoring schemes typically involve instruments such as LCR meters or impedance analyzers to directly measure R_{ESR} and C . However, these methods are costly and require manual intervention, limiting their practicality. In contrast, online techniques, which include real-time and quasi-online schemes are widely used for capacitor condition monitoring. These methods estimate capacitance by analyzing voltage and current dynamics under varying conditions. Real-time online techniques are particularly advantageous as they allow continuous health monitoring without interrupting converter operation. For example, a signal-injection-based method has been proposed to estimate capacitance using Fourier analysis of total harmonic distortion [7]. Quasi-online techniques, on the other hand, require temporarily halting system operations to estimate capacitance. For instance, a zero-vector injection method has been applied in a three-phase inverter [8] and the LLC primary bridge [9], enabling voltage changes to be observed and analyzed.

Despite these advancements, current studies face two critical challenges in the condition monitoring of resonant tank capacitors. First, most existing estimation methods are designed for low- and mid-frequency bands, which are unsuitable for the high operational resonant frequencies of resonant tanks. Sec-

(a) Full-bridge topology.

(b) Resonant tank fundamental harmonic approximation circuit.

Fig. 1: Topology of the full-bridge LLC resonant converter.

ond, to achieve higher estimation accuracy, dedicated voltage and/or current sensors and charging/discharging circuits are often employed. However, these setups require high-frequency, high-precision sampling devices, significantly increasing monitoring costs.

To address these challenges, a novel capacitance estimation method is proposed for the condition monitoring of LLC resonant tank capacitors. The primary contributions of this method are: 1) its applicability to high-frequency resonant tanks, and 2) its ability to function without the need for additional equipment, making it a cost-effective and practical solution.

II. THEORY OF OPERATION

This section provides an overview of LLC converters, their components, and the selection of resonant tank capacitors.

A. Structure of LLC Resonant Converter

The LLC resonant converter is a highly efficient and versatile isolated DC/DC converter widely utilized across various applications. It is favored for its compact size, lightweight design, high efficiency, bi-directional operation, and capability to manage a broad input voltage range. The inherent ZVS feature significantly reduces switching losses, making it suitable for high-power-density applications such as renewable energy systems and electric vehicle chargers [10]. A full-bridge LLC topology is illustrated in Fig. 1 (a).

The main components of an LLC converter include:

1) Primary side inverter: Typically comprising MOSFETs arranged as a square-wave generator, this inverter produces a unipolar square-wave voltage by alternating the MOSFETs' switching at approximately 50% duty cycle. Properly dead-time periods between switching transitions prevent cross-conduction and enable ZVS.

2) Resonant circuit: This network consists of the resonant capacitor (C_r), series resonant inductor (L_r), and transformer magnetizing inductor (L_m). It facilitates efficient energy transfer, with the transformer's primary winding receiving a bipolar square-wave voltage. The transformer also provides electrical isolation and adjusts the output voltage via its turns ratio.

The equivalent model of the LLC resonant circuit is depicted in Fig. 1 (b), derived using the fundamental harmonic analysis (FHA) method without accounting for secondary leakage inductance. Here, V_{ac} represents the fundamental harmonic of the resonant network input voltage, V_{rec} is the fundamental harmonic of the transformer primary-side voltage, and Z_{eq} denotes the equivalent load impedance [10].

3) Secondary rectifier network: Typically comprising diodes in a full-bridge configuration, this rectifier converts the AC input into DC output for the load (R_L). An output capacitor is included to stabilize the rectified voltages and currents. For higher efficiency in low-voltage, high-current applications, synchronous rectification using MOSFETs is often employed to minimize conduction losses.

For LLC resonant converter, the series resonant frequency f_r , parallel resonant frequency f_m , normalized switching frequency f_n , quality factor Q , and inductor ratio K are defined as:

$$f_r = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{L_r C_r}} \quad (1)$$

$$f_m = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{(L_r + L_m)C_r}} \quad (2)$$

$$f_n = \frac{f_s}{f_r} \quad (3)$$

$$Q = \frac{\sqrt{L_r/C_r}}{Z_{eq}} \quad (4)$$

$$K = \frac{L_m}{L_r} \quad (5)$$

$$Z_{eq} = \frac{8N^2}{\pi^2} R_L \quad (6)$$

where f_s represents the resonant frequency, N denotes the turns ratio of the transformer.

B. Resonant Tank Capacitor Selection

The selection of capacitors is a critical aspect of resonant tank design. Common options include Aluminum Electrolytic Capacitors (Al-Caps), Metallized Polypropylene Film Capacitors (MPPF-Caps), and Multi-layer Ceramic Capacitors (MLCCs). Resonant capacitors must exhibit a low dissipation factor (DF) to handle the high-frequency and high-magnitude currents typical in resonant tanks. Al-Caps and MLCCs, despite their advantages in other applications, generally have higher DF and are less suitable for these scenarios. NP0 capacitors, with their low DF, can be used but are limited by their restricted capacitance range. Consequently, MPPF-Caps are often preferred in resonant tank applications due to their

very low DF and ability to handle high-frequency currents effectively.

III. PROPOSED MONITORING SCHEME

A. Capacitor Failure Mechanisms and Aging Indicators

Capacitors in resonant tanks are subject to failures caused by a variety of intrinsic and extrinsic factors, including design flaws, material degradation, operating conditions (e.g., temperature, voltage, and current), and environmental influences such as moisture and mechanical stress. Failures typically fall into two categories:

1) Catastrophic failures: These occur suddenly due to over-stress events, such as voltage or current surges exceeding the capacitor tolerance, resulting in immediate functionality loss.

2) Wear-out failures: These develop gradually as the materials degrade over time, reducing the capacitor efficiency and effectiveness until it no longer meets performance standards.

Common EOL indicators include significant deviations in C and R_{ESR} from their initial values (C_0 , R_{ESR0}). Tab. II summarizes the typical EOL criteria for Al-Caps, MPPF-Caps, and MLCCs.

The failure mechanisms of MPPF-Caps can be broadly categorized into two primary factors: dielectric breakdown and electrode corrosion [11]. Dielectric breakdown, often caused by overvoltage, occurs at localized weak points in the capacitor. These initial breakdowns are typically cleared through the self-healing process, allowing the capacitor to regain its functionality with only a negligible reduction in capacitance. However, as the number of isolated weak points increases, the overall capacitance gradually diminishes, eventually leading to the capacitor reaching its end-of-life [12]. Moisture absorption and the resulting corrosion of the metallized layer also significantly contribute to the aging process. Electrode corrosion can be divided into two types: atmospheric corrosion, which occurs in the absence of voltage stress, and electrochemical corrosion, which is driven by the application of an AC voltage. Research indicates that under an AC field, the corrosion of the metallized layer is a major factor contributing to the failure of metallized film capacitors [13].

B. Proposed Capacitance Estimation Approach

To enhance the reliability and efficiency of MPPF-Caps in LLC resonant tanks, a novel capacitance estimation method is proposed. This technique monitors the input and output voltages of LLC converters over time, effectively eliminating the need for additional sensors.

Based on Fourier analysis, the resonant tank input voltage can be calculated as follows:

$$V_{ac} = \frac{2n}{\pi} V_{in} \sin(2\pi f_s t) \quad (7)$$

TABLE II: Typical end-of-life criteria of capacitors.

	Al-Caps	MPPF-Caps	MLC-Caps
End-of-life criteria	$C/C_0 < 80\%$ $R_{ESR}/R_{ESR0} > 2$	$C/C_0 < 95\%$	$C/C_0 < 90\%$

with its RMS value given by:

$$V_{ac,RMS} = \frac{\sqrt{2}n}{\pi} V_{in} \quad (8)$$

where $n = 1$ and 2 for half bridge and full-bridge primary side inverters, respectively.

On the output side, the fundamental voltage of the transformer primary-side voltage can be calculated as:

$$V_{rec} = \frac{4N}{\pi} V_o \sin(2\pi f_s t - \psi_v) \quad (9)$$

with the RMS value expressed as:

$$V_{rec,RMS} = \frac{2\sqrt{2}N}{\pi} V_o \quad (10)$$

where ψ_v is the phase angle.

Therefore, the voltage gain (M) of the resonant tank can be formulated as:

$$M = \frac{V_{rec,RMS}}{V_{ac,RMS}} = \frac{2NV_o}{nV_{in}} \quad (11)$$

Notably, based on FHA model, as in Fig. 1 (b) and using the voltage divider law, the voltage gain can also be defined by the ratio between V_{rec} and V_{ac} as:

$$M = \frac{V_{rec}}{V_{ac}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{[(1 - \frac{1}{f_n^2})Qf_n]^2 + [(1 - \frac{1}{f_n^2})\frac{1}{K} + 1]^2}} \quad (12)$$

Detailed deduction process can be found in [10].

By combining the voltage gain derived from the resonant tank (11) and FHA model (12), along with the Eqs. (1)-(6), the capacitance of the resonant capacitor can be estimated using the following relationship:

$$\hat{C}_r = \frac{1}{4L_r\pi^2 f_s^2 \left(1 - \frac{L_m Z_{eq} (\sqrt{-4L_m^2 M^2 \pi^2 f_s^2 + X_{eq}^2} - M Z_{eq})}{L_r M X_{eq}^2}\right)} \quad (13)$$

where

$$X_{eq}^2 = 4L_m^2 \pi^2 f_s^2 + Z_{eq}^2 \quad (14)$$

Remark 1: As noted from (13), the proposed estimation method relies on the resonant frequency, the resonant tank voltage gain, and the equivalent load impedance. The resonant frequency is assumed to match the reference frequency generated by the controller via a voltage-controlled oscillator (VCO). The voltage gain and the equivalent load impedance can be calculated using equations (11) and (6), respectively, ensuring the practicality and accuracy of the proposed approach. The steps for implementing the capacitance estimation method are detailed in Algorithm 1.

Remark 2: The proposed capacitor estimation method for assessing capacitor health in resonant tank utilizes existing voltage measurement points integrated into the converter control system. Therefore, no additional sensors are required to implement the monitoring method.

Algorithm 1: The proposed capacitance estimation approach for MPPF-Caps in resonant tank.

Input: Resonant tank parameters L_r , L_m . Input and output voltage measurements of LLC converter V_{in} , V_o .

Output: Estimated capacitance \hat{C}_r .

1. Generate reference resonant frequency using VCO.
2. Calculate the secondary impedance with (6).
3. Determine the voltage gain of the resonant tank using (11).
4. Estimate the MPPF-Cap capacitance with proposed approach outlined in (13).

TABLE III: LLC converter parameters.

Rated input voltage	540 V
Rated output voltage	28 V
Rated power	3 kW
Turns ratio N	10:1
Resonant inductance L_r	$6.8 \mu H$
Magnetizing inductance L_m	$34 \mu H$
Resonant capacitance C_r	$0.09 \mu F$
Switching frequency	160 kHz-350 kHz

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

To verify the proposed estimation method, simulations are performed in MATLAB and PLECS environments. The topology and parameters of the LLC converter used in these simulations are shown in Fig. 1 (a) and TAB. III. Three case scenarios were performed to assess the robustness of the proposed estimation method under various conditions, including load changes, inductance variations, and capacitance degradation. Figs. 2 to 4 present the output voltage, current, resonant capacitor voltage, current, and estimation results for the LLC converter in these scenarios.

A. Load Change Condition

In this scenario, the converter initially operates under normal conditions at a load of 750 W. At 10 ms, the load is increased to 1500 W, and at 20 ms, the load is decreased. The estimation results indicate that the proposed method maintains accurate capacitance monitoring without errors, even under varying load conditions. This demonstrates the robustness of the method in adapting to dynamic load changes.

B. Inductance Change Condition

In this scenario, the resonant inductance is increased by 10% of its nominal value at 10 ms and decreased by 10% at 20 ms. Despite these variations, the proposed estimation method consistently delivers excellent performance, accurately tracking the capacitance value without errors. This highlights the reliability of the method in scenarios involving inductance fluctuations.

C. Capacitance Degradation Condition

In this scenario, the resonant capacitor gradually degrades, experiencing a rapid 3.9% reduction over 30 ms (with a 5% reduction considered a failure). The estimation results

(a) LLC converter dynamics.

(b) Zoomed-in LLC converter dynamics.

Fig. 2: LLC dynamics under load change conditions.

show that the proposed method successfully tracks the gradual degradation of the capacitance, demonstrating its capability to provide accurate and reliable estimations even under progressive deterioration conditions.

V. CONCLUSION AND REMARKS

This paper proposes a novel capacitance estimation method for the online condition monitoring of MPPF-Caps in the resonant tank of LLC converters. Utilizing Fourier analysis and the FHA model, the capacitance estimation method is developed by analyzing the voltage gain of the resonant tank. The primary advantages of the proposed condition monitoring method are: 1) The method analyzes the input and output voltages of the LLC converter, eliminating the need to measure the high-frequency ripple of capacitors, and 2) The implementation relies solely on the sensors already integrated for converter control, avoiding the need for additional sensor installations. The feasibility and effectiveness of the proposed method are validated through simulation results. Future work will focus on implementing the proposed method in real-world LLC converters to verify its performance and practicality.

(a) LLC converter dynamics.

(b) Zoomed-in LLC converter dynamics.

Fig. 3: LLC dynamics under inductance change conditions.

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(a) LLC converter dynamics.

(b) Zoomed-in LLC converter dynamics.

Fig. 4: LLC dynamics under capacitance degradation conditions.

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